

Non-linear Carrier Interactions in Lead Halide Perovskites and The Role of Defects.

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Abstract

The simple solution processability at room temperature exposes lead halide perovskite semiconductors to a non-negligible level of unintentional structural and chemical defects. Ascertained that their primary optoelectronic properties meet the requirement for high efficiency optoelectronic technologies, a lack of knowledge about the nature of defects and their role in the device operation currently is a major challenge for their market-scale application due to the lack of stability and reliability. Here, we use excitation correlation photoluminescence (ECPL) spectroscopy to investigate the recombination dynamics of the photo-generated carriers in lead bromide perovskites and quantitatively describe the carrier trapping dynamics within a generalization of the Shockley-Read-Hall formalism. The superior sensitivity of our spectroscopic tool to the many body interactions enables us to identify the nature and energetics of the defects unambiguously. In the case of polycrystalline films, depending on the synthetic route, we demonstrate the presence of both deep and shallow carrier traps. The shallow defects which are situated at about 20meV below the conduction band dope the semiconductor leading to a substantial enhancement of the photoluminescence quantum yield in spite of carrier trapping. At excitation densities relevant for lasing we observe breakdown of the rate-equation model indicating a build-up of a highly correlated regime of the photo-carrier population that suppresses the non-radiative

1 Auger recombination. Furthermore we demonstrate that colloidal nanocrystals represent virtually
2 defect-free systems, suffering from non-radiative quenching only due to sub-picosecond Auger like
3 interactions at high excitation density. By correlating the fabrication conditions to the non-radiative
4 loss channels, this work provides guidelines for material engineering towards superior opto-electronic
5 devices.

6 **Introduction:**

7 Lead halide perovskite semiconductors have shown their potential application in a variety of opto-
8 electronic technologies due to their high refractive index, excellent light harvesting capability and
9 suitable emission and optical gain properties¹. They have a direct band gap in the visible energy range,
10 with large oscillator strength associated to an exciton transition close to the band edge². Efficient
11 screening results in binding energies ranging from a few to tens of meV^{3,4} and accordingly, at room
12 temperature and excitation densities relevant for photovoltaic and light emitting devices, i.e. below
13 10^{17}cm^{-3} , there is predominant population of ionized states (electron-hole plasma)^{3,5}. However, the *free*
14 carriers are highly susceptible to trapping at defects associated to intra-gap states, limiting the device
15 performances. This gives rise to a *density dependent* branching of the recombination paths and strongly
16 influences the carrier lifetimes and photoluminescence quantum yields (PLQY). Although PLQY up to
17 90% has been demonstrated in well passivated colloidal nanocrystals^{6,7}, polycrystalline thin films have
18 PLQYs hardly above 30% at excitation densities below 10^{17}cm^{-3} ⁸. Furthermore at high excitation
19 densities ($> 10^{17}\text{cm}^{-3}$), typical for the lasing regime, many body Auger recombination opens a new
20 channel for the population loss^{9,10}. For an effective device optimization, it is primordial to comprehend
21 and quantify the limiting mechanisms influencing the carrier dynamics.

22 Based on time-resolved PL (Tr-PL) spectroscopy measurements at different experimental conditions,
23 the recombination dynamics in methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) and bromide (MAPbBr₃)
24 perovskites have been largely described within the Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) framework^{9,11,12}, where-
25 in the carriers are assumed to be trapped at *deep defect* states within the band-gap. Accordingly, the
26 population dynamics are described by a simple rate equation, $\frac{dn}{dt} = G - k_1n - k_2n^2$, where G is the
27 generation rate, k_1 and k_2 are the monomolecular trapping and bimolecular radiative recombination
28 rates respectively. However, given the varied nature of defects that the perovskite films are prone to,
29 such a simplistic description may not suffice to provide a comprehensive photo-physical picture. There
30 are experimental^{13,14} and theoretical evidences¹⁵⁻²⁰ for the existence of both shallow and deep level

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3 1 traps arising from an assortment of point, surface or linear defects, with each of them displaying
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5 2 distinct photo-physical characteristics. For example, charged shallow defects may dope the material
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7 3 and not necessarily form recombination centres, whilst neutral deep traps act as non-radiative
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9 4 quenchers of the excited state population. Importantly, it has been suggested that their selective
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11 5 manifestation in the film is governed by the specific precursor chemistry at the fabrication stage^{15,21,22}
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13 6 as well as the post-fabrication conditions^{23,24,25}.

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15 7 Conventional PL techniques fail to capture such rich but complex defect physics, owing to their
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17 8 inability to identify the nature of carrier traps unambiguously and model free. Though they enable the
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19 9 measurement of various recombination rates, including the trapping rates, they do not distinguish
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21 10 between different kinds of traps and possible doping and excitonic effects, which are left as variable
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23 11 out-comes of numerical analysis of the decays¹³. Measurements of intensity dependent steady-state
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25 12 quantum yields can give crucial hints in choosing appropriate photo-physical scenarios^{5,21}, yet they are
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27 13 seldom performed in conjunction with the time-resolved measurements. The variability of the nature
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29 14 and density of defects with the fabrication route and experimental conditions adds complexity to the
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31 15 problem and call for methods that can intrinsically distinguish myriad non-radiative decay paths.

32 16 In this work we employ ECPL Spectroscopy²⁶⁻²⁸ which has inherent sensitivity to the non-linear
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34 17 interactions among the excited carriers and thus provides unique insights into the non-radiative decay
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36 18 channels. We investigate the recombination dynamics in lead bromide perovskites and explore the
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38 19 influence of the fabrication route. In polycrystalline thin films, where the perovskite is crystallized
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40 20 directly on the substrate as in most of the operating devices, we *demonstrate the presence of both deep*
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42 21 *trap states as well as shallow defects* which induce unintentional doping and *quantitatively* assess their
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44 22 influence on the density dependent recombination dynamics in thin films of MAPbBr₃ perovskite. Their
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46 23 respective manifestation depends on the fabrication protocol, in particular, we note that an excess of
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48 24 halogen mitigates the presence of detrimental deep trap states. In fact, in the alternative case of
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50 25 CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals, which are grown as colloids in the presence of excess halogen, we observe that
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52 26 the recombination mechanism is dominated by radiative electron-hole recombination thus
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54 27 demonstrating that there is no intrinsic limitation in the material performances. However, they still
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56 28 suffer from non-radiative Auger recombination when the average number of photo-excitations per
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58 29 nanocrystal exceeds ~ 0.15 , depleting the population in the sub-picosecond timescale.

57 30 **Results and Discussion:**

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3 1 We first perform ECPL experiments on MAPbBr₃ perovskite thin films prepared by two different
4 fabrication routes. MA-1 is fabricated with equimolar material precursors (PbBr:MABr – 1:1) in a
5 2 single step, while MA-2 is obtained in presence of an excess of MABr (1:1.05). The UV-Vis
6 3 absorption and cw-PL spectra of these samples, reported in Figures 1a and 1b, show that they exhibit
7 4 very similar optical characteristics. Both the films are characterized by an absorption onset at
8 5 approximately 2.35 eV, with an excitonic resonance at 2.37 eV. Following Elliott analysis (see Section
9 6 S1 of SI) of the absorption spectra, we obtain very similar exciton binding energies of 42 meV and 47
10 7 meV for MA-1 and MA-2 respectively. We compare these samples with a colloidal suspension of
11 8 CsPbBr₃ cubic nanocrystals of approximate size of 7 nm. The nanocrystals have a blue-shifted band-
12 9 edge and a stronger excitonic peak, owing to the non-negligible quantum confinement (Figure 1c). The
13 10 PL from all the samples are Stokes shifted by about 30 meV with respect to the excitonic transition in
14 11 the linear absorption. We note that MA-1 exhibits very low PLQY of < 1% at excitation densities
15 12 slightly greater than 10¹⁶cm⁻³, while MA-2 shows higher yield of about 4% at similar densities (and
16 13 under ambient atmosphere). This is in line with recent reports, which show that the presence of excess
17 14 Br at the fabrication stage results in films with higher luminescence yields, though this observation has
18 15 not been categorically rationalized²⁹. On the other hand, NCs show very high PLQY of about 75%,
19 16 representing a very efficient system for light emission. The structural analysis of the samples is shown
20 17 in Section S1 of the SI.
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Figure 1: UV-Vis absorption and PL spectra of (a) MA-1 and (b) MA-2 thin films made with different precursor concentrations and of (c) colloidal suspension of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. Plotted as grey lines in the top two panels are the free carrier and excitonic absorption spectra obtained from Elliott analysis of the total absorption.

In the ECPL experiment (schematically represented in Figure 2) we measure the time integrated PL upon photo-excitation with two temporally delayed pump pulses of equal intensity, I_{pump} , and energy, 3.1 eV. The total intensity of the collected PL in the presence of both the pulses can be written as²⁷,

$$PL(I_{pump}, \tau) = \int_0^{\infty} PL_1(I_{pump}, t) dt + \int_{\tau}^{\infty} PL_2(I_{pump}, t) dt + \int_{\tau}^{\infty} PL_{cross}(2I_{pump}, t, t - \tau) dt \quad [1]$$

where τ is the delay between the pulses. The first two terms in [1] represent the PL due to each of the pump pulses separately, while the third term arises from the non-linear mixing of the photo-excited population. ECPL signal represents the fraction of this non-linear term over the total PL and thus can be written simply as $ECPL(\tau = 0, I_{pump}) = \frac{PL(2I_{pump}) - 2PL_1(I_{pump})}{PL(2I_{pump})}$, at zero-delay between the pulses. By scanning the delay between the pulses, we obtain the photo-excitation dynamics with a temporal resolution limited only by the pulse-width, in the present case, ~ 150 fs. Being a lock-in based

heterodyne technique (see Methods), ECPL also offers higher S/N ratios in comparison to the conventional streak camera or photon counting systems.

An ideal scenario of pure radiative regime, with either geminate ($\frac{dn}{dt} = -An + G$) or bimolecular ($\frac{dn}{dt} = -Bn^2 + G$) recombination, results in a linear growth of steady-state PL with the excitation density. According to equation [1], this will give rise to a null ECPL signal. The presence of density dependent competing non-radiative channels bestows a super-linear or sub-linear behaviour of the PL with intensity, resulting in a non-zero ECPL signal. For example, within the SRH formalism with deep traps, the PL increases with intensity as $I^{1.5}$ (see Section S2 of SI for a detailed analysis). In such a scenario, the largest, *positive*, ECPL signal achievable is approximately 30%, at $\tau=0$ delay. Auger-like processes, which yield a sub-linear dependence of the PL on the intensity ($I^{0.6}$) and give rise to a *negative* ECPL peak. Thus ECPL specifically picks out the contribution of the limiting non-radiative channels from the overall recombination dynamics and provides greater precision in the analysis than conventional techniques.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of Excitation Correlation – Photoluminescence (ECPL) experiment.

Figures 3a and 3c show the relative PLQY (see Methods) plotted as a function of the excitation density for MA-1 and MA-2 respectively. The trends of ECPL taken at zero-delay between the pulses are also shown for both the samples. In Figures 3b and 3d, we show the ECPL dynamics taken at different

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3 1 excitation densities, for MA-1 and MA-2 respectively. The symmetry in the dynamics along the zero-
4 delay is due to the reciprocity of the two pulses.
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8 3 We first consider the case of the MA-1 thin films whose relative PLQY exhibits a monotonic increase
9 with the excitation density (Figure 3a). This clearly indicates the density dependent quenching of the
10 4 non-radiative path, here assigned to the trapping of the photo-generated carriers. As the excitation
11 5 density becomes closer to and then above the available trap density, most of the traps are filled, leaving
12 6 substantial free-carrier population for radiative recombination resulting in higher PLQY. At very large
13 7 densities (close to 10^{18} cm^{-3}), additional non-radiative channels open up, reducing the yield.
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19 9 At excitation density of about 10^{16} cm^{-3} we observe an ECPL signal of about 11% (Figures 3a and 3b),
20 which exhibits no decay at least within the 600 ps window. The positive sign of the signal fits well with
21 10 the trap limited behaviour as discussed earlier. The lack of any dynamics in the measured time range
22 11 indicates that recombination lifetimes are in the nanosecond time scale. As the excitation density is
23 12 further increased, the system moves towards the linear radiative regime due to trap filling, reducing the
24 13 ECPL signal. At excitation densities beyond $3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, a kinetic appears in the ECPL time trace
25 14 with the signal becoming negative close to the zero-delay and at the highest excitation density used.
26 15 We assign this to the non-radiative auger recombination process and accordingly the observed
27 16 dynamics directly corresponds to the auger rate.
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36 18 Moving to the case of MA-2 film, we find that the intensity dependence of the relative PLQY, shown in
37 19 Figure 3c, follows a similar trend to that of MA-1, highlighting again a trap-limited recombination
38 20 process, albeit it remains pretty insensitive to excitation intensity, over about two decades, before
39 21 increasing. Note that the absolute PLQY is considerably higher in this case than in MA-1. The ECPL is
40 22 however suggesting a different, and an apparently contradicting scenario. Firstly, the ECPL response,
41 23 shown in Figures 3c and 3d, is close to zero at low excitation densities, which, in complete contrast to
42 24 the case of MA-1, suggests a trap-less efficient radiative recombination. Secondly, the ECPL increases
43 25 to a maximum of about 15% upon increasing the excitation density up to 10^{17} cm^{-3} , clearly revealing the
44 26 saturation of trap states. Note in addition that at all the excitation densities there is a distinct ECPL
45 27 dynamic with decay time of about 500 ps. At excitation densities above $3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ the ECPL
46 28 signal drops and a negative dip develops around zero-delay.
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Figure 3- (a) MA-1 and (c) MA-2: relative PLQY and zero-delay ECPL signal plotted as a function of excitation density. (b) MA-1 and (d) MA-2: ECPL dynamics at different excitation densities – experimental data is plotted as symbols while the solid lines are the numerical fits

For a quantitative analysis of the intensity and the dynamics of the ECPL, we consider a comprehensive model detailed within the set of rate-equations [2-4] and schematically represented in Figure 4.

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = G - R - \gamma_t(N_t - n_t)n + \gamma_d n_t - \gamma_{auger} n^2 p \quad [2]$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = G - R - \gamma_r n_t p - \gamma_{auger} n^2 p \quad [3]$$

$$\frac{dn_t}{dt} = \gamma_t(N_t - n_t)n - \gamma_r n_t p - \gamma_d n_t \quad [4]$$

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3 1 In Equations [2-4] G is the generation rate, given by the light absorption. $R = B_{rad}np$ represents the
4 radiative bimolecular recombination dictated by the recombination coefficient B_{rad} . γ_t represents the
5 carrier-trapping rate and we assume predominant electron trapping; N_t represents the total available
6 trap density; γ_r represents the non-radiative recombination of the trapped electron with hole; γ_d is the
7 de-trapping rate: if the electron (hole) is trapped within a deep level, this rate is negligible, while in the
8 case of shallow traps, this term cannot be neglected. γ_{Auger} represents the non-radiative Auger rate that
9 is relevant at higher densities. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the electrons are
10 predominantly trapped, though the model can be easily extended even for hole traps. Unlike the usual
11 formalism used in the literature which considers only the dynamical evolution of the carrier population
12 with a mono-molecular trapping rate, we consider a set of coupled equations accounting for electron,
13 hole and trap densities, with no presumptions on the nature of carrier trapping.

14 12 By fitting the ECPL of MA-1 with such a model we obtain a trap density of around $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$;
15 $B_{rad} = 2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $\gamma_{Auger} = 1 \times 10^{-27} \text{ cm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $\gamma_t = 0.84 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\gamma_r = 0.19 \times$
16 $10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (the complete list of parameters is listed in Section S3.1 of SI). Overall these
17 experiments provide a quantitative description of the trap limited electron-hole recombination for
18 perovskites within the SRH framework, as already proposed in previous studies^{12,13}.

19 17 If we employ the same photo-physical model (Figure 3c, with deep traps) to fit the ECPL response of
20 MA-2 at low density ($\sim 18 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), we retrieve an extremely high B_{rad} of about $2.2 \times$
21 $10^{-6} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. This is about three orders of magnitude higher than that of MA-1 and it would give rise
22 to a PLQY of almost unity. More importantly, to account for the increase of the ECPL signal (Figure
23 3c) and to fit the dynamics at higher excitation densities we would need to introduce an inverse density
24 dependence for this coefficient (see Section S3.2 of SI). B_{rad} is however an intrinsic material property,
25 correlated to the electronic structure through its dependence on the bandgap and the transition moments
26 between the bands³⁰. Thus, with similar chemical composition and identical optical signatures, MA-2
27 must exhibit very similar B_{rad} as MA-1 and show no dependence on the excitation density. This makes
28 the fit unphysical, and calls for a refinement of the photo-physical scenario.

Figure 4: a) Photo-physical scenario of MA-1 with deep trap as the primary non-radiative channel. b) Model used for MA-2, with shallow donors that dope the material and also act as non-radiative recombination centres.

Virtually null ECPL response suggests an almost linear dependence of PL ($\propto B \cdot n \cdot p$) on intensity at low density, instead of the 3/2 power of the previous case. Such a linear dependence in the presence of trapping process can be explained by assuming the existence of shallow donors (or acceptors), which are thermally ionized to dope the material, apart from creating non-radiative recombination centres (represented in Figure 4b). Doping manifests itself in the charge neutrality condition as $n + n_t = N_D + p$ (where n, p, n_t and N_D are the electron, hole, filled trap and doping densities respectively), resulting in a large background doping $n \cong N_D$, even in the dark. Supposing the shallow defects are n-doping the material, at low excitation density p is proportional to the light intensity I and $n \cong N_D$. PL is linear with excitation intensity I because it stems from the radiative recombination of the photo-generated holes ($p \sim I$) and the doping electrons ($n \cong N_D$). Accordingly the ECPL response (see Section S2.4 of SI) is negligibly small. At higher intensity, the photo-generated electron density becomes comparable to background doping and thus participate in the radiative process albeit in competition with carrier trapping, which results in a positive ECPL signal. It can be shown analytically, that the zero-delay ECPL response *increases* almost linearly with excitation density (Section S2.4 of SI). This can be

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3 1 directly perceived in the linear trend of the zero-delay ECPL signal till an excitation density of about
4 2 10^{17}cm^{-3} in Figure 4a, with the onset and slope of the rise dictated by the doping concentration. Note
5 3 that such a background doping and presence of shallow traps mitigate the non-radiative losses, which
6 4 can in fact explain the higher PLQY observed in MA-2 with respect to MA-1.
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11 5 We performed a quantitative analysis of the ECPL dynamics of MA-2 with the set of equations [2-4],
12 6 considering the modified charge neutrality condition accounting for doping, and a non-negligible de-
13 7 trapping rate, relevant for a shallow traps as illustrated in Figure 4b. We note that the observed ECPL
14 8 dynamics here correspond mainly to the sub-nanosecond trapping by the available shallow donor states.
15 9 The complete list of the resulting parameters is reported in Section S3.3 of SI. We retrieve a donor
16 10 density of about $2 \times 10^{18} \text{cm}^{-3}$ and a trapping rate, γ_t of $3 \times 10^{-8} \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$, which are much higher
17 11 than in the case of MA-1, in agreement with the shift of the relative PLQY slope to higher excitation
18 12 density. Importantly, the estimated value of B_{rad} is now back to the value found in MA-1 as expected
19 13 for an intrinsic characteristic of the material.
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Figure 5: a) MA-2 - Intensity dependence of time-zero ECPL signal at 77K and 290 K. b) Natural logarithm of the time-zero ECPL signal taken at a fixed excitation density of $3 \times 10^{15} cm^{-3}$, plotted against $1/k_B T$ where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature.

Ionization of the donor/acceptor states, responsible for the doping, is a thermal mediated process. The doping density (N_D) is hence proportional to the term: $exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_d}{kT}\right)$, where ΔE_d is the energy of the defect state within the bandgap with respect to the bottom of the electronic bands and represents the defect ionization energy. Following such a relation, one would expect a reduced doping concentration at lower temperatures. Since the ECPL signal follows the ratio between the excitation density and the

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3 1 background doping (see Section S2.4), this would increase the ECPL response. To verify this, we
4 2 performed measurements at 77K and in Figure 5a we show the intensity dependence of the zero-delay
5 3 ECPL signal at 77K plotted along with the signal taken at 290K. At a fixed low excitation density of
6 4 about $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, we find that (i) the ECPL response increases from 0.8% at 290K to about 8% at
7 5 77K and (ii) the progressive ECPL trend shifts to lower excitation densities at 77K with respect to the
8 6 RT case. Both observations are in good agreement with the expected reduction in background doping.
9 7 From the amount of shift we can roughly write the doping concentration at 77K as
10 8 $N_D(77K) \sim 0.1 N_D(290K)$, from which we can make a quick estimation of the defect ionization
11 9 energy as about 20 meV. The inverse proportionality between the ECPL signal and the doping
12 10 concentration leads to a linear relationship between $\ln(ECPL)$ and $1/kT$ as shown in Figure 5b, with
13 11 the measurement performed at a fixed excitation density of $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The slope of this curve is
14 12 given by ΔE_d , which can be fitted to be $19.6 \pm 1.7 \text{ meV}$, in agreement with our assumption of shallow
15 13 defects. Interestingly, a recent report Cho et al²⁹ shows that when MAPbBr₃ thin films are synthesised
16 14 in presence of excess of MABr the work function of the semiconductor is reduced.

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19 15 Recent theoretical works have primarily suggested that most of the intrinsic point defects in lead halide
20 16 perovskites form shallow carrier traps^{17,31-33}. Due to the large formation energies theoretically
21 17 predicted for the deep defect states, their role in the carrier recombination must be negligible. This is in
22 18 agreement with our observation in MA-2, where the primary carrier traps are shallow defects.
23 19 Nevertheless formation of deep defects that are associated with the halogen have also been suggested
24 20 ^{34,16}. Buin et al¹⁵ have in fact shown under “halogen-poor” conditions in MAPbBr₃ that Br vacancies
25 21 form deep trap states with large ionization energies. This is in agreement with the recombination
26 22 dynamics of MA-1 sample presented here, which is more prone to Br vacancies than MA-2, which is
27 23 on the contrary prepared in a “halogen-rich” condition.

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30 24 Moving to the analysis of the ECPL signal beyond excitation densities of 10^{17} cm^{-3} in the case of MA-
31 25 2, we note that the model breaks down and it is unable to account for the drop in ECPL signal. Indeed
32 26 keeping B_{rad} fixed, leads to a growing ECPL signal well above the observed maximum value of 15%.
33 27 By considering Auger non-radiative recombination to reverse this trend, an abrupt drop in the PLQY is
34 28 predicted but it is not observed.

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37 29 The new regime in MA-2 at high excitation density could be explained by a density dependent
38 30 renormalization of the carrier-carrier interaction screening leading to the increase in carrier correlation.

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4 plasma which reduces the interactive term in Equation [1]. Coalescence of carriers into a stable exciton
5 2 plasma which reduces the interactive term in Equation [1]. Coalescence of carriers into a stable exciton
6 requires the release of the energy to the lattice. In this material the expected binding energy is 3 to 5
7 3 requires the release of the energy to the lattice. In this material the expected binding energy is 3 to 5
8 4 times larger than the LO phonon energy at thermodynamic equilibrium, requiring a multi phonon
9 5 emission process that is quite unlikely. However, the exciton binding energy reduces with carrier
10 6 density, as a result of e-h plasma screening. A simple estimate of the bandgap renormalization³⁵ from
11 7 screening gives ~ 60 meV at $3 \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$, and ~ 100 meV at 10^{18}cm^{-3} with the typical square root
12 8 scaling with density. Therefore, just in the density range of the peculiar ECPL response, exciton
13 9 formation could occur via the emission of a *single* LO phonon. This process could thus occur with
14 10 higher probability than any other multi-phonon phenomena. Note that this interpretation is fairly robust
15 11 because at slightly larger densities, Mott transition occurs, with the full disappearance of the exciton
16 12 binding, but still preserving the geminate recombination path. Our explanation is qualitative, because
17 13 the carrier density is quickly decreasing in time, leading to the superposition of different regimes and
18 14 the simultaneous interplay between screening, Mott transition, and eventually exciton formation. While
19 15 these complex dynamics are clearly well beyond the simple free-carrier model presented in Eqs. (2-4),
20 16 our results capture the essence of the carrier interactions in perovskites under different regimes. The
21 17 selective expression of the geminate regime only in MA-2 can be partly related to higher film quality
22 18 with lower deep trap density. This may in turn reduce the Auger scattering, thus enabling a substantial
23 19 carrier population to be available for radiative recombination.

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30 20 We also note that all the measurements reported in Figure 3 are carried out on samples that are kept
31 21 under constant illumination of high intensity pulses before starting the experiment and in vacuum, in
32 22 order to reduce PL instabilities. Indeed before stabilizing, the PLQY reduces in minutes and
33 23 accordingly the ECPL at a fixed excitation intensity increases (Figures S2 and S3 in SI). This indicates
34 24 that the available trap density is increasing on very slow timescales, possibly associated to photo-
35 25 induced formation of deep-trap complexes as suggested by Agiorgousis et al¹⁶.

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49 26 Having investigated the role of defects in thin films, we turn our attention towards colloidal
50 27 suspensions of nanocrystals (NCs) of CsPbBr₃, which exhibit PLQY as high as 75% even at low
51 28 excitation densities^{6,36}, indicating minimum role of defects. Note that, changing the cation from MA⁺ to
52 29 Cs⁺, the thin films exhibit very similar characteristics as MA-2 sample (see Figure S4 in SI) and thus
53 30 we are not introducing additional variability. We consider here nanocrystals with average size of
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6.7 \pm 1 nm, whose UV-Vis absorption and PL spectra are reported in Figure 1. The PL decay kinetics are mono-exponential with a lifetime of about 4 ns suggesting pure excitonic emission³⁶.

Figure 6: a) ECPL dynamics of colloidal suspension of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals taken at different pump intensities. b) ECPL (top panel) and relative PLQY (bottom panel) plotted as a function of average number of excitations per particle. The experimental data is plotted as symbols and theoretical estimates (see main text) plotted as solid lines.

In figure 6a, we report the ECPL collected from the NCs sample at different excitation intensities. Under low excitation, we obtain a zero ECPL response substantiating the efficient excitonic nature of the emission. As the pump intensity is increased, the signal becomes *negative* monotonically, however keeping the same kinetics. The negative ECPL response can be attributed to Auger like quenching of the excited state population in the ultrafast timescales. This is in fact even more evident when looking at the dynamics close to the time-zero which shows an ultrafast decay (< 250 fs).

In the case of the NCs, it is intuitive to estimate the average number of excitations per nano-crystal rather than excitation density. Assuming that the value of absorptivity (α in cm^{-1}) at 3.1 eV (corresponding to bulk carrier absorption) for NCs is similar to that of the film, which is evaluated to be around 10^4 cm^{-1} , the average number of carriers on each nanocrystal can be evaluated as $\langle N \rangle = \sigma \phi_{\text{photon}}$ where $\sigma = \alpha V$ (V is the volume of the NC) is the cross-section and ϕ_{photon} is the photon

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3 1 flux. We obtain a cross section of about $3 \times 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2$, in agreement with the estimates of Makarov
4 et al³⁷. As shown in Figure 6b, the negative ECPL starts to increase significantly when $\langle N \rangle > 0.15$.
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6 3 This approximately coincides with the carrier density at which the PLQY starts to drop from its
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8 5 maximum value.

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11 5 When the number of the photo-excitations per particle exceeds one, Auger interactions bring the
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13 7 population back to less than one within 1 ps. Therefore, after certain pump intensity, only one photon is
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15 9 emitted irrespective of the injected density. Overall the fast non-radiative de-excitation results in a
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17 11 saturation of the PL emission, as also seen as a reduction of the relative PLQY in Figure 6b. As a
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19 13 consequence, the first pump pulse will saturate the PL emission and the photo-excitations created by
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21 15 the delayed pulse are quenched by the ultrafast Auger interactions resulting in detrimental contribution
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23 17 to the PL ($\Delta PL < 0$). The PL decays with the intrinsic exciton lifetime thus resulting in a mono-
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25 19 exponential ECPL dynamics independent of the pump intensity.

26 13 The trends shown in Figure 6b can be analytically reproduced by considering the probability (p_m) of
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28 15 finding m excitons in a nanocrystal, given by a Poisson distribution $p_m = \frac{\langle N \rangle^m}{m!} e^{-\langle N \rangle}$. Following
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30 17 ultrafast Auger recombination, each photo-excited nanocrystal is left with only one exciton for
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32 19 radiative recombination. In such a scenario, PL is proportional to the sum, $(p_1 + p_2 + \dots) = 1 - p_0 =$
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34 21 $1 - e^{-\langle N \rangle}$ ³⁸. Accordingly, we can estimate PLQY as $\frac{1 - e^{-\langle N \rangle}}{\langle N \rangle}$ and ECPL as $(1 - e^{-2\langle N \rangle}) - 2(1 -$
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36 23 $e^{-\langle N \rangle})$, which are plotted as solid lines in Figure 6b³⁹ and they closely follow the experimental trends.
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38 25 It must be noted that Auger recombination occurs before the onset of optical gain and hence presents the
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40 27 main limiting channel in lasing applications, as also shown recently by Makarov et al³⁷. On the
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42 29 contrary, in the low excitation density regime, the NCs represent a clean material system with no
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44 31 detrimental trapping processes reducing the yield.

52 25 **Conclusions**

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55 26 In this work, we quantitatively assess the impact of defects and unintentional doping on the carrier
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57 28 dynamics in lead bromide perovskites by exploiting ECPL to extract the nonlinear part of the
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59 30 recombination process. The polycrystalline films of MAPbBr₃ synthesized by using a virtually

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3 1 equimolar concentration of the precursors exhibit SRH like recombination mediated by the presence of
4 2 deep carrier traps. On the contrary, the sample synthesized in the presence of an excess of MABr shows
5 3 clear evidence of shallow defects. In particular we show that these shallow defects are located
6 4 approximately 20 meV below the conduction band and they can be ionized leading to the doping of the
7 5 crystal and in turn partly alleviate the non-radiative quenching of the carrier population. Our results
8 6 thus demonstrate the intrinsic correlation between the nature and density of defects in these materials
9 7 and the fabrication route and provides mechanistic framework to engineer materials with high quantum
10 8 yields. We also quantitatively fit the ECPL dynamics with appropriate photo-physical models and
11 9 obtain a set of relevant photo physical constants, such as bimolecular recombination coefficient,
12 10 $B_{rad} \sim 2 \times 10^{-9} \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ and Auger rate, $\gamma_{Auger} \sim 1 \times 10^{-27} \text{cm}^6 \text{s}^{-1}$, that compete above densities of
13 11 10^{18}cm^{-3} . Furthermore we report here for the first time a highly correlated regime of the carrier
14 12 population, where geminate recombination becomes predominant, as long as the role of non-radiative
15 13 recombination centers is mitigated. This is assigned to a renormalization of the band gap due to
16 14 screening at high excitation density that competes and somehow limits the Auger recombination loss,
17 15 otherwise detrimental for lasing applications. Finally we demonstrate that colloidal nanocrystals
18 16 provide a handle to create defect free perovskites, though they still suffer from ultrafast Auger
19 17 recombination that quenches the PL in the high excitation regime.
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37 19 **Experimental Methods:**

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42 21 *MAPbBr3 thin films - MA-1:* The equimolar solution of lead bromide (PbBr_2) and methylammonium
43 22 bromide ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Br}$) is prepared in anhydrous N,N-dimethylformamide (20 wt%) and spin coated on
44 23 clean glass at 3000 rpm for 60 seconds, and immediately annealed at 100°C for 15 minutes.
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48 24 *MA-2:* A solution of PbBr_2 and $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Br}$ with a molar ratio of inorganic to organic of 1 to 1.05, is
49 25 prepared in anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (40 wt%). The sample is prepared following the nanocrystal
50 26 pinning recipe reported by Cho et al²⁹. The spin-coating speeds used were 500 rpm for 7 seconds and
51 27 3000 rpm for 90 seconds. After the initial acceleration, the perovskite solution is dropped on the
52 28 substrate. After 60 seconds nanocrystal pinning is initiated by chlorobenzene. The sample is
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3 1 subsequently annealed at 90°C for 10 minutes. All the samples are encapsulated in a poly-methyl
4 methacrylate film before being exposed to ambient conditions.

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7 3 *CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals*: The colloidal suspensions are prepared as described by Akkerman et al⁶.

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10 4 *Excitation Correlation PL*:

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13 5 The laser system consists of a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire oscillator (Coherent Micra) that provides ~
14 20fs pulses centered around 800nm at 80MHz. The pulses are amplified using a regenerative amplifier
15 6 (Coherent RegA 9000) at 250KHz and compressed using a grating based compressor to generate ~50 fs
16 7 pulses with pulse energy of 6 μJ. Pump pulses for the ECPL experiment are generated via frequency
17 8 doubling of the 800 nm pulses in a BBO crystal. The beam is then split using a thin beam splitter to
18 9 generate two pump pulses with one of them sent through a computer controlled translation stage to
19 10 achieve variable delay between them. Each of the pump pulse is modulated at distinct frequencies (381
20 11 Hz and 272 Hz) using an optical chopper. They are then focused onto the sample with a lens of focal
21 12 length ~ 150mm. The PL from the sample is then collected onto a slow silicon photodiode, after
22 13 filtering out the pump with a long-pass optical filter. The output of the photodiode is simultaneously
23 14 fed into a lock-in amplifier and an oscilloscope to measure ΔPL and PL respectively. The lock-in
24 15 amplifier is referenced at the sum frequency (653 Hz) to selectively measure the fractional PL due to
25 16 non-linear interactions.
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29 18 *Relative PLQY*:

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32 19 The excitation source is same as the ECPL experiment. The PL is collected and focused into a fiber
33 20 coupled to a spectrometer (Ocean Optics Maya pro 2000). To obtain relative PLQY at each excitation
34 21 density, the spectrally integrated PL is divided by the pump power.

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37 22 **Associated Content**:

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40 23 Supporting Information: Section S1 – Sample characterization; Section S2 – How to interpret ECPL
41 24 response; Section S3 – ECPL Fitting results. This material is available free of charge via internet at
42 25 <http://pubs.acs.org>
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46 26 **Author Information**

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49 27 Corresponding author: annamaria.petrozza@iit.it. ARSK and SN contributed equally to this work.
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Notes:

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References

- (1) Stranks, S. D.; Snaith, H. J. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2015**, *10*, 391–402.
- (2) Srimath Kandada, A. R.; Petrozza, A. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 536–544.
- (3) D’Innocenzo, V.; Grancini, G.; Alcocer, M. J. P.; Kandada, A. R. S.; Stranks, S. D.; Lee, M. M.; Lanzani, G.; Snaith, H. J.; Petrozza, A. *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 3486.
- (4) Miyata, A.; Mitioglu, A.; Plochocka, P.; Portugall, O.; Wang, J. T.-W.; Stranks, S. D.; Snaith, H. J.; Nicholas, R. J. *Nat. Phys.* **2015**, *11*, 582–587.
- (5) Saba, M.; Quochi, F.; Mura, A.; Bongiovanni, G. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2016**, *49*, 166–173.
- (6) Akkerman, Q. A.; D’Innocenzo, V.; Accornero, S.; Scarpellini, A.; Petrozza, A.; Prato, M.; Manna, L. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 10276–10281.
- (7) Yakunin, S.; Protesescu, L.; Krieg, F.; Bodnarchuk, M. I.; Nedelcu, G.; Humer, M.; De Luca, G.; Fiebig, M.; Heiss, W.; Kovalenko, M. V. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 8056.
- (8) Deschler, F.; Price, M.; Pathak, S.; Klintberg, L. E.; Jaraush, D.-D.; Higler, R.; Huttner, S.; Leitjens, T.; Stranks, S. D.; Snaith, H. J.; Atature, M.; Phillips, R. T.; Friend, R. H. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, *5*, 1421–1426.
- (9) D’Innocenzo, V.; Srimath Kandada, A. R.; De Bastiani, M.; Gandini, M.; Petrozza, A. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 17730–17733.
- (10) Milot, R. L.; Eperon, G. E.; Snaith, H. J.; Johnston, M. B.; Herz, L. M. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2015**,

- 1
2
3 1 25, 6218–6227.
4
5
6 2 (11) Yamada, Y.; Nakamura, T.; Endo, M.; Wakamiya, A.; Kanemitsu, Y. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**,
7
8 3 *136*, 11610–11613.
9
10 4 (12) Saba, M.; Cadelano, M.; Marongiu, D.; Chen, F.; Sarritzu, V.; Sestu, N.; Figus, C.; Aresti, M.;
11
12 5 Piras, R.; Geddo Lehmann, A.; Cannas, C.; Musinu, A.; Quochi, F.; Mura, A.; Bongiovanni, G.
13
14 6 *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 5049.
15
16 7 (13) Stranks, S. D.; Burlakov, V. M.; Leijtens, T.; Ball, J. M.; Goriely, A.; Snaith, H. J. *Phys. Rev.*
17
18 8 *Appl.* **2014**, *2*, 34007.
19
20 9 (14) Baumann, A.; Vath, S.; Rieder, P.; Heiber, M. C.; Tvingstedt, K.; Dyakonov, V. *J. Phys. Chem.*
21
22 10 *Lett.* **2015**, *6* (12), 2350–2354.
23
24 11 (15) Buin, A.; Comin, R.; Xu, J.; Ip, A. H.; Sargent, E. H. *Chem. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 4405–4412.
25
26
27 12 (16) Agiorgousis, M. L.; Sun, Y.; Zeng, H.; Zhang, S. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 14570–14575.
28
29 13 (17) Duan, H.-S.; Zhou, H.; Chen, Q.; Sun, P.; Luo, S.; Song, T.-B.; Bob, B.; Yang, Y. *Phys. Chem.*
30
31 14 *Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *17*, 112–116.
32
33
34 15 (18) Jung, M.-C.; Lee, Y. M.; Lee, H.-K.; Park, J.; Raga, S. R.; Ono, L. K.; Wang, S.; Leyden, M. R.;
35
36 16 Yu, B. D.; Hong, S.; Qi, Y. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2016**, *108*, 073901.
37
38
39 17 (19) Kim, J.; Lee, S. H.; Lee, J. H.; Hong, K. H. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, *5*, 1312–1317.
40
41 18 (20) Wetzelaer, G. J. A. H.; Scheepers, M.; Sempere, A. M.; Momblona, C.; Avila, J.; Bolink, H. J.
42
43 19 *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 1837–1841.
44
45
46 20 (21) Wen, X.; Feng, Y.; Huang, S.; Huang, F.; Cheng, Y.; Green, M.; Ho-baillie, A. *J. Mater. Chem.*
47
48 21 *C* **2015**, *4*, 793–800.
49
50 22 (22) Fang, X.; Zhang, K.; Li, Y.; Yao, L.; Zhang, Y.; Wang, Y.; Zhai, W.; Tao, L.; Du, H.; Ran, G.
51
52 23 *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2016**, *108*, 071109.
53
54
55 24 (23) Leijtens, T.; Srimath Kandada, A. R.; Eperon, G.; Grancini, G.; D’Innocenzo, V.; Ball, J. M.;
56
57 25 Stranks, S. D.; Snaith, H. J.; Petrozza, A. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 15451–15459.
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1 (24) Fang, H.-H.; Wang, F.; Adjokatse, S.; Zhao, N.; Loi, M. A. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2016**
4
5 2 *DOI: 10.1002/adfm.201600715.*
6
7
8 3 (25) Aristidou, N.; Sanchez-Molina, I.; Chotchuangchutchaval, T.; Brown, M.; Martinez, L.; Rath,
9
10 4 T.; Haque, S. A. *Angew. Chemie* **2015**, *54*, 8208–8212.
11
12 5 (26) von der Linde, D.; Kuhl, J.; Rosengart, E. *J. Lumin.* **1981**, *24/25*, 675–678.
13
14
15 6 (27) Borgwardt, M.; Sippel, P.; Eichberger, R.; Semtsiv, M. P.; Masselink, W. T.; Schwarzburg, K. *J.*
16
17 7 *Appl. Phys.* **2015**, *117*, 215702.
18
19 8 (28) Rosen, D.; Doukas, A. G.; Budansky, Y.; Katz, A.; Alfano, R. R. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **1981**, *39*,
20
21 9 935–937.
22
23
24 10 (29) Cho, H.; Jeong, S.-H.; Park, M.-H.; Kim, Y.-H.; Wolf, C.; Lee, C.-L.; Heo, J. H.; Sadhanala, A.;
25
26 11 Myoung, N.; Yoo, S.; Im, S. H.; Friend, R. H.; Lee, T.-W. *Science*. **2015**, *350* (6265), 1222–
27
28 12 1225.
29
30 13 (30) Filippetti, A.; Delugas, P.; Mattoni, A. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2014**, *118*, 24843–24853.
31
32 14 (31) Yin, W.-J.; Shi, T.; Yan, Y. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2014**, *104*, 063903.
33
34
35 15 (32) Du, M. H. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2014**, *2*, 9091.
36
37
38 16 (33) Shi, H.; Du, M. H. *Phys. Rev. B* **2014**, *90*, 174103.
39
40 17 (34) Du, M.-H. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2015**, *6*, 1461–1466.
41
42
43 18 (35) Trankle, G.; Leier, H.; Forchel, A.; Haug, H.; Ell, C.; Weimann, G. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1987**, *58*,
44
45 19 419–422.
46
47 20 (36) Akkerman, Q. A.; Motti, S. G.; Srimath Kandada, A. R.; Mosconi, E.; D’Innocenzo, V.; Bertoni,
48
49 21 G.; Marras, S.; Kamino, B. A.; Miranda, L.; De Angelis, F.; Petrozza, A.; Prato, M.; Manna, L.
50
51 22 *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 1010–1016.
52
53
54 23 (37) Makarov, N. S.; Guo, S.; Isaienko, O.; Liu, W.; Robel, I.; Klimov, V. I. *Nano Lett.* **2016**, *16*,
55
56 24 2349–2362.
57
58 25 (38) Klimov, V. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2000**, *104*, 6112–6123.
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(39) Since the PLQY is about 75% even at low excitation, due to other non-radiative recombination processes, we rescaled $\langle N \rangle$ accordingly to account for this loss channel.

TOC Graphic

